

COMPOUND VERBS IN KARAKALPAK, ENGLISH AND GERMAN
LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article studies the compound verbs in three different languages: Karakalpak, English and German. In the article main features of compound verbs are identified, analyzed and compared from morphological and structural point of view.

Keywords: compound verbs, verb, verbal stem, noun, adjectives, part of speech, helping verb, compound constructions, category, component, morphological structure.

Verbs as a part of speech play a key role in the vocabulary of each language and structurally they can be compound, phrasal and auxiliary types. In the following research compound verbs in the three languages are studied from the point of view of the structure and formation.

In Karakalpak language compound verbs are, in general, formed by combining two verbs or matching a part of speech with a verb. In result of compounding, they together give another new lexical meaning. So, linguists divide Karakalpak compound verbs into three categories¹:

1. Compound verbs with a different part of speech as a first component. In these compounds as a second component will serve the helping verbs like *et, al, ber, qoy, sal, bol, ko'r, qal, basla, jet* and others.

a) Among them the helping verb 'et' is mostly combined with abstract nouns and form a compound verb. They are widespread in the Karakalpak language: *qariz etiw, diqqat etiw, ta'rbiya etiw, hu'rmet etiw, iqlas etiw, dawam etiw, xabar etiw, inam etiw etc.*

b) The helping verb 'bol' is combined with nouns, adjectives and modal words. For instance: *abad boliw, suw boliw, qayil boliw, shad boliw, tamam boliw, qapa boliw, qiyin boliw, awir boliw, qurg'in boliw, oylasiq boldi, ko'z qulaq bol, saw bol, duwshar bol, bek bol, joq bol, kerek bol* and so on.

c) The helping verb 'ber' goes together with abstract nouns and form a compound verb: *wa'de beriw, sa'lem beriw, esap beriw, juwap beriw, baha beriw, dawis ber, ja'rdem beriw, ma'slahat beriw, dawis beriw, komanda beriw etc.*

d) Compound verbs with the helping verb 'al': *dem al, xabar al, juwap aliw, ha'wij aliw, qol alisiw, aldin aliw, esapqa aliw, sabaq al, ta'lim al, qolg'a al, tilge al, eske al, kewilge aliw* and so on.

e) The verb 'sal' together with nouns form compound constructions: *na'zer saliw, ku'sh saliw, g'ayrat saliw, qiyqiy saliw, ja'r saliw, shtraf saliw, tiyim saliw etc.*

f) compound verbs with the element qoy often come together with nouns and onomatopoeias: *qa'dem qoyiw, qol qoyiw, bas qoyiw, kewil qoyiw, hayt qoyiw, g'iyt qoyiw.*

¹ "Ha'zirgi qarqalpaq a'debiy tilinin' grammatikasi", Bilim baspasi, 1994, p 65

g) The helping verb *ko'r* in combination with nouns, adjectives serves to form a compound verb: *jaqsi ko'riw, jek ko'riw, an'sat ko'riw, jaman ko'riw, ilayiq ko'riw, ku;n ko'riw* and others.

h) compound verbs with a component *qal*: *kewil qaliw, azapqa qaliw, tan' qaliw, bos qaliw, hayran qaliw* and so on.

2. Compound verbs with a verbal stem (Feyil tiykarli qospa feyiller): Verb + verb structure.

These compounds are made up of the connection of two notional verbs. As in other types of compounds, in the compound verbs the second component, i.e. the second verb takes grammatical categories (changes in the person, form). The number of the verbs serving as a second component is not so many, they are about thirty. The basic notional verbs used to form a compound verb are the followings²: *al, ber, bar, kel, ket, shiq, jat (jatir), tur, otir, qoy, jiber, tasla, o't, qayt* and others. For ex: *qazip al, satip al, sorap al*.

a) Compound verbs with the verb 'ber': *quyip ber, salip ber, tigip ber, tazalap ber, alip ber, shig'arip ber*.

b) Compound verbs with the verb 'bar'. Compound verbs of this type point out the directedness of the action to somewhere: *aydap bar, jetip bar, kirip bar, ko'rip bar* etc.

c) Compound verbs with the stem 'kel'. Compounds of this type are the antonyms of the previous subgroup of compounds with the stem 'ber'. For instance: *kirip kel, ko'rip kel, izlep kel, aytip kel, bilip kel, jetip kel, qaytip kel*.

d) Compounds with the stem 'shiq': *kirip shiq, alip shiq, aytip shiq, aydap shiq, ko'rip shiq, sanap shiq*.

e) Compounds with the stem 'jatti' (jatir): *so'yalesip jatti, sezip jatti, shayqalip jatir, oylanip jatir, sezip jatir, uyqilap jatir* etc.

3. Analytical form of the verb. The first component of these verbs can be either a helping verb or any part of speech, but the last component is always a verb. If the first constituent is a noun or adjective or any other part of speech, then the second component will be a helping verb. If the first component is a verb, then the second component will be a notional verb. The analytical way of formation can have the following morphological structure: notional Verb + helping Verb. In Karakalpak language the following verbs occupy the function of helping verbs: *basla, bol, otir, tur, ju'r, jatir (atir), bar, kel, al ber, qoy, ko'r, tasla, sal, shiq, tu's, jet, qara, baq, jo'nel, qash, qayt, o't, tart, ur, tap, et (qil), de*. These verbs can do both: they can be a component of compound verbs, saving their lexical meaning and can be used as independent notional verbs. For ex: *oqiy basla, jaza basla, jazip bol, aytip bol, oqip bol, ko'rip bol, oqip tur, jazip tur, aytip tur* etc.

Compound verbs in English

Compound verbs in English are considered to be controversial in Linguistics. I.V. Arnold states that the problem indeed can be argued in several different ways. He

² "Ha'zirgi qarqalpaq a'debiy tilinin' grammatikasi", Bilim baspasi, 1994, p 66

also admits that it is not even clear whether verbal compositions exist in present-day English, though such verbs as *outgrow*, *overflow*, *stand up*, *black-list*, *stage-manage* and *whitewash* are often called compound verbs. There are even more complications to the problem than meet the eye. H. Marchand, whose work has been quoted so extensively in the present chapter, treats *outgrow* and *overflow* as unquestionable compounds, although he admits that the type is not productive and that locative particles are near to prefixes³. "The Concise Oxford Dictionary", on the other hand, defines *out-* and *over-* as prefixes used both for verbs and nouns; this approach classes *outgrow* and *overflow* as derivatives, which seems convincing. The *stand-up* type was in turns regarded as a phrase, a compound and a derivative; its nature has been the subject of much discussion.

The verbs *blackmail* and *stage-manage* belong to two different groups because they show different correlations with the rest of the vocabulary.

blackmail v __ *honeymoon* v __ *nickname* v

blackmail n *honeymoon* n *nickname* n

The verbs *blackmail*, *honeymoon* and *nickname* are, therefore, cases of conversion from endocentric nominal compounds. The type *stagemanage* may be referred to back-formation. The correlation is as follows:

stage-manage v _ *proof-read* v _ *housekeep* v

stage-manager n *proof-reader* n *housekeeper* n

The second *element* in the first group is a noun *stem*; in the second group it is always verbal. Some examples of the first group are the verbs *safeguard*, *nickname*, *shipwreck*, *whitewash*, *tiptoe*, *outline*, *honeymoon*, *blackmail*, *hero-worship*. All these exist in English for a long time. The 20th century created *week-end*, *double-cross* 'betray', *stream-line*, *softpedal*, *spotlight*. The type is especially productive in colloquial speech and slang, particularly in American English⁴.

The second group is *less numerous* than the first but highly productive in the 20th century. Among the earliest coinages are *backbite* (1300) and *browbeat* (1603), then later *ill-treat*, *house-keep*. The 20th century has coined *hitch-hike* (c f. *hitch-hiker*) 'to travel from place to place by asking motorists for free rides'; *proof-read* (c f. *proof-reader*) 'to read and correct printer's proofs'; compare also *mass-produce*, *taperecord* and *vacuumclean*. The most recent is *hi-jack* 'make pilots change the course of aeroplanes by using violence' which comes from the slang word *hi-jacker* explained in the Chambers's Dictionary as 'a highwayman or a robber and blackmailer of bootleggers' (smugglers of liquor)⁵. Thus I.V. Arnold points out the peculiar features of the English compound verbs, which are controversial issues of the modern linguistics.

The structural integrity of these combinations is supported by the order of constituents which is a contrast to the usual syntactic pattern where the verb stem would come first. C f. *to read proofs* and *to proofread*. H. Marchand calls them p s e u d o - c

³ I.V. Arnold "The English Word", M: Высшая школа, 1986, p 126

⁴ I.V. Arnold "The English Word", M: Высшая школа, 1986, p 126

⁵ I.V. Arnold "The English Word", M: Высшая школа, 1986, p 127

om p o u n d s, because they are created as verbs not by the process of composition but by conversion and back-formation. His classification *may seem convincing*, if the vocabulary is treated diachronically from the viewpoint of those processes that are at the back of its formation. It is quite true that the verb *vacuum-clean* was not coined by compounding and so is not a compound *genetically (on the word-formation level)*. But if we are concerned with the present-day structure and follow consistently the definition of a compound given in the opening lines of this chapter, we see that it is a word containing two free stems. It functions in the sentence as a separate lexical unit. It seems *logical to consider such words as compounds* by right of their structural pattern.

Furthermore, R. S. Ginzburg also considers compound verbs as a special subgroup among compound words. He admits that there are many polymorphic verbs that represented of two morphemic sequences of two root-morphemes, like *to weekend*, *to gooseflesh*, *to spring-clean*, but derivationally they are all words of secondary derivation in which the existing compound nouns only serve as bases for derivation.

They are often termed pseudo-compound verbs. Such polymorphic verbs are presented by two groups⁶:

1) verbs formed by means of conversion from the stems of compound nouns as in *to spotlight* from a *spotlight*, *to sidetrack* from a *side-track*, *to handcuff* from *handcuffs*, *to blacklist* from a *blacklist*, *to pinpoint* from a *pin-point*;

2) verbs formed by back-derivation from the stems of compound nouns, e.g. *to babysit* from a *baby-sitter*, *to playact* from *play-acting*, *to housekeep* from *house-keeping*, *to spring-clean* from *spring-cleaning*.

Besides Ginzburg mentions of a small group of compound verbs made up of the combination of verbal and adverbial stems that language retains from earlier stages, e.g. *to bypass*, *to inlay*, *to offset*. However, he also notes that this type of compounding is no longer productive in modern English.

Compound verbs in German

Compounding is not so much productive in the formation of verbs, as it does with nouns in German. The compound verbs also consist of two immediate constituents, the last of which is a verb. As the first component different parts of speech can serve. For ex: *teilnehmen*, *stattfinden*, *freilassen*.

Compound verbs in German can have the following structures:

- a) Verb + Verb - *kennen lernen*, *spazieren gehen*, *stehenbleiben*
- b) Noun (Substantiv) + Verb - *teilnehmen*, *stattfinden*, *achtgeben*, *Radfahren*
- c) Adjective (Adjektiv) + Verb - *freisprechen*, *stillstehen*, *klarmachen*, *bekanntmachen*, *vollgiessen*
- d) Numeral (Zahlwort) + Verb - *einteilen*, *vierteilen*
- e) Adverb (Adverb) + Verb - *weiterfahren*, *fortsetzen*, *nahelegen*, *fernsehen*, *zuru"ckgehen*
- f) Participle (Partizip) + Verb - *verlorengehen*, *gefangennehmen*.

⁶ R.S. Ginzburg and others "A Course in Modern Lexicology", Москва, «Высшая Школа», 1979, p 148

Apart from that, compound verbs in German are different from compound verbs of other languages with their spelling. In the German language compound verbs are graphically similar to verbs with separable prefixes. In the sentences the two components of the compound verbs are written separately. In contrast to the compound verbs in Karakalpak and English, that are written either hyphen or solidly, German compound verbs are written with a break, while used in the context. For instance, **Radfahren, fernsehen: Am Abend fahre ich Rad. Alle Familie sieht am Sonntag fern.**

Conclusion

From the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that compound verbs are more common in Karakalpak and German, while in English verbs as compounds is one of the controversial subjects in linguistics. Karakalpak and German compound verbs are mainly formed with the help of both noun and verbal stems and German compounds considerably differ in the way that they are written separately while used in the sentence. English linguists such as Arnold and Ginzburg consider them as pseudo compounds, and that the affixes, verbs made up of can be seen as prefixes, so the compound verbs as a subtype of compound words in English ought to be further studied.

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